

Graphene as sensitive platform for determination of 4-nitrophenol

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Abstract : Herein we report the electroanalytical determination of 4-nitrophenol (4-NP) using glassy carbon electrode and graphene modified glassy carbon electrode. Glassy carbon electrode (GCE) does not show a peak corresponding to the electrooxidation of 4-NP whereas the commercial graphene (CG) modified glassy carbon electrode (CG/GCE) exhibits an oxidation peak at 0.10 V corresponding to the oxidation of 4-nitrophenol. From cyclic voltammetric studies, it is observed that the sensitivity of graphene modified glassy carbon is two-fold higher than that of glassy carbon electrode.

Keywords : Graphene, 4-nitrophenol, environmental pollutant, electrooxidation, electrochemical sensor.

Introduction

4-NP is one of the toxic chemical that requires the development of simple, fast, sensitive, and accurate analytical method for its detection and quantification is needed. A number of methods have been employed for determination of 4-NP, many of them involving very laborious, tedious and time consuming methods such as spectrophotometric methods^{1,2}, high performance liquid chromatography³, high performance capillary electrophoresis⁴ and gas chromatography⁵. Electrochemical methods⁶⁻⁹ have received considerable attention in the determination of nitrophenols due to their great advantages, such as easy, simple operation, fast response, good sensitivity and *in situ* detection. The estimation which focuses the reduction of 4-NP would be affected with by the dissolved oxygen in the solvent. To remove any dissolved oxygen, the solution should be saturated with nitrogen/argon. This process makes the whole determination process more tedious and less reliable in monitoring of 4-NP. In this work we want to investigate the application of commercial graphene as a novel electrode material in the electrochemical oxidation of 4-NP. Graphene, the one-atom-thick two dimensional honeycomb lattice of sp²-bonded carbon, has attracted huge attention from scientific research groups, thanks to its unique nanostructure

and unusual properties such as high charge transport mobility¹⁰ and high electrocatalytic activities¹¹.

In this work, direct oxidative determination of 4-NP was attempted by applying electrochemical technique to a GCE modified with CG. We investigated here whether graphene nanomaterials exhibit any advantage for 4-NP detection when compared to that of bare GCE.

Results and discussion

Fig. 1 shows the cyclic voltammogram in presence of 2 mM of ferricyanide/ferrocyanide at GCE and CG/GCE. The voltammogram clearly is indicative of the electron transport conduction of the electrodes. In case of bare GCE, the peak to peak separation was found to 620 mV. But for CG/GCE was found to be 600 mV. This reduction in peak to peak may attributed to the adsorptive properties of CG with the redox couple and/or it may exert a synergistic effect by mass transport properties.

Fig. 2 shows the cyclic voltammogram in presence and absence of 1 μM 4-NP at GCE and CG/GCE. No oxidation and reduction peaks were observed for PBS in the absence of 4-NP at CG/GCE which suggests that the CG is electrochemically inactive in the selected potential range of -1.0 to +1 V. In the presence of 4-NP, a well-defined reduction peak at -0.82 V (E_{pc}) and an oxidation

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammetric response of 2 mM ferrocyanide/ferricyanide of (left) bare and (right) CG/GCE.

peak at 0.1 V for CG/GCE, and peak at -0.83 V (E_{pc}) for GCE with no oxidation peak were observed. From this it is clear that the oxidation of 4-NP observed at CG/GCE shows higher current response when compared to that of GCE along with a negative shift in peak potential in comparison with GCE. This higher current response of CG may be attributed to the mass transport properties of CG along with the edge plane exposure¹². CG have very strong adsorption property with 4-NP because of the multiple

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammetric response of 1 mM 4-NP at bare GCE (—) and CG/GCE (-----).

interaction between them. The interaction through π - π stacking between the CG and 4-NP may also take place. As anticipated, the oxidation peak current at CG/GCE was higher, indicating that CG has good electrocatalytic activity for 4-NP oxidation, which can evidently increase the current response and thereby decrease the detection limit. The sensitivity of CG/GCE has been synergistic.

The scan rate effect on the electrooxidation of 1 μ M 4-NP at CG/GCE was investigated to study the kinetics of the electrode reaction (Fig. 3). From the double logarithmic plot of $\log(v)$ vs $\log(I_{pa})$, the slope value was found to be 0.91 which resembles that the electron transfer process is adsorption controlled (Fig. not shown). The relationship between E_{pa} and $\ln(v)$ was noted that the E_{pa} changes linearly with $\ln(v)$ (Fig. not shown). On substituting the values and simplifying the Laviron equation, we got a value of 0.6 for electron transfer coefficient (α) and 1.316 s⁻¹ for rate constant (k_s) for the modified electrode.

Experimental

Reagents :

Graphene and 4-nitrophenol were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used as received. Double distilled water was used throughout the experiment.

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammetric response of 1 mM 4-NP at different scan rates from 10–100 mV s⁻¹.

Fabrication procedure :

The electrochemical experiments were performed on a CHI 1100A electrochemical instrument using the CG/GCE and bare GCE as working electrode, a platinum wire was the counter electrode, and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) was the reference electrode. The CG/GCE was fabricated by the following method : The GCE was highly polished with alumina slurry and washed successively with double-distilled water and ethanol. Then, the dispersion of 1 mg of CG into 1 mL of ethanol was sonicated to make a homogeneous dispersion. Finally, 5 μL of the CG dispersion was coated onto the GCE and dried in air. Thus, CG/GCE was obtained.

Conclusion

From the cyclic voltammetry analysis it clearly indicates that the CG/GCE showed a well defined excellent oxidation peak at 0.1 V whereas the bare GCE does not

exert any oxidation peak at that potential. This demonstrates that the CG/GCE can be potentially applied for environmental sensing applications. So that various kinds of nitro containing pollutants may be clearly analysed at real times.

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